

VIRTUAL INTELLIGENT EYE VISION (VIEV): FOR BLIND / PARTIAL VISION IMPAIRMENT USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE OF THINGS (AIoT)

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Abstract:

The requirement for independent living is acknowledged in today's high-tech environment for visually impaired people, who mostly struggle with social isolation. They struggle in unfamiliar settings without any manual assistance. Most tasks rely on visual information, so those who are blind or visually impaired are at a disadvantage because they lack access to this crucial information. Recent developments in inclusive technology make it possible to increase the assistance provided to those with visual impairment. The project “Virtual Intelligent Eye Vision (VIEV) for blind / partial vision impairment using Artificial Intelligence of Things (AIoT)” is suggested to use text recognition, artificial intelligence, machine learning, the internet of things, and IoT to assist folks who are blind or visually impaired. This proposal's main goal is to add features like Chabot's, image and voice assistants, face and object recognition, object identification, and text extraction from e-books. This project This project can help by using voice commands to recognize things in the immediate environment, text analysis to identify the text in a hard copy document, and face recognition to identify a person. It will be a productive approach for blind individuals to use technology to engage with their surroundings and take advantage of its features. The tool is being created to aid in the ability of millions of blind and visually impaired persons to avoid moving impediments or to detect, sense, and grip objects in advance and environment. The project “*Virtual Intelligent Eye Vision (VIEV) for blind / partial vision impairment using Artificial Intelligence of Things (AIoT)*” enables visually impaired people to see the world through technology. It is able to describe the scene in front of the user, and also assist users through various sensors support.

Keywords: AI, IoT, Machine learning, AIoT, VIEV, OpenCV, Vision Impairment.